

Clinical and Psychosocial Profile of Patients Attempting Suicide: A Cross-Sectional Observational Study

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Suicide continues to pose a significant challenge to public health systems globally, affecting individuals across all age groups, ethnicities, and socioeconomic status. Understanding the clinical and psychosocial background of such individuals is critical to framing targeted interventions. **Aim:** To study the clinical and psychosocial profile of patients attempting suicide. **Methods:** A cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the emergency department of tertiary care hospital, 100 consecutive adult patients with history of attempted suicide were recruited. After taking written informed consent, structured questionnaire was used to record sociodemographic and clinical variables. Suicide Intent Scale (SIS), Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale-21(DASS-21) and Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) were used to assess psychiatric morbidity and socioeconomic status was assessed by modified BG Prasad scale. Appropriate statistical methods were used. **Results:** Suicide attempt was more common in males (56%), among 21–30 years (43%), married (62%), unemployed (67%) and middleclass individuals. Most common method was ingestion of poisonous substance (90%), primarily phenol and organophosphate. Seventy eight percent patients had a history of psychiatric illness, 60% had high suicide intent (SIS ≥ 29), and severe depression, anxiety, and stress were seen in 57%, 58%, and 61%, respectively. Severe psychiatric symptoms indicated by high BPRS score ≥ 75 was noted in 78% of cases. High suicide intent, severe psychiatric symptoms and severe levels of depression, anxiety and stress was observed more among young, married, unemployed and in individuals. **Conclusion:** High psychiatric morbidity and suicide intent among young adults calls for urgent mental health evaluation, socioeconomic support, and preventive mental health strategies in emergency settings.

Keywords: *Suicide attempt, Clinical profile, Psychosocial factors, SIS, DASS-21, BPRS, Psychiatric morbidity*

INTRODUCTION:

Suicide attempt is self-directed, potentially injurious behavior that is carried out with the intent to end one's life.^[1] According to WHO, suicide was the 8th leading cause of Potential years of life lost (PYLL) globally in 2004 among individuals aged 15 to 44 years.^[2] In India, data from the National crime records bureau (NCRB) reveals a steady and troubling increase in suicide rates over the years. The suicide rate, which stood at 9.9 per lakh population in 2017,^[3] has seen a consistent upward trend, reaching 12.4 per lakh in 2022.^[4] Suicide is a multifactorial issue that results in significant familial, societal, and economic losses, and has emerged as a serious social concern requiring more intensive and targeted intervention. In depth understanding of the risk

factors, history taking, psychosocial background of these patients is crucial for preventing suicide. Identifying the underlying factors behind suicide attempts can assist mental health professionals and policymakers in early diagnosis, timely intervention, appropriate treatment, and the formulation of effective suicide prevention strategies. This study was conducted to retrospectively explore the psychosocial dimensions of individuals who have attempted suicide using standardized psychiatric assessment tools.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Study type and location:

After obtaining institutional ethical committee approval, 100 consecutive patients attending the

emergency of Government medical college, Patiala during the study period (01-8-2023 to 31-07-2024) with alleged history of suicide attempt and meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled into this study. **Inclusion criteria** were (1) Patients above >18 years of age (2) Patients with alleged history of suicide attempt (3) Patients giving written informed consent. **Exclusion criteria** were (1) Patients less<18 years of age (2) Patients not willing to give written informed consent (3) Patients with altered mental status. Patients with impaired consciousness or patients who were unwilling to participate were excluded. Written and informed consent in the language of patients was obtained from the patient beforehand. Detailed history was obtained from the patient and his/her attendant, thorough clinical examination was done and these patients were managed as per the standard protocols. When patients were stable, psychosocial assessment of the patient was done using Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) used in this study for assessing the positive, negative and affective symptoms of individuals who have psychotic disorders and the individual's behavior prior to suicide attempt was also considered. Each item was rated on a 7 point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not present) to 7 (extremely severe), generating a total score between 18 and 126. ^[5]

Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) is a set of 21 items of three self-report scales designed to further the process of defining, understanding and measuring clinically significant emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress^[6] Suicide Intent Scale (SIS) which consists of 20 items which assess the severity of an individual's desire to die at the time of a suicide attempt and assess the risk of future attempts The SIS scale classifies suicidal intent levels as low (15-19),medium (20-28) or high (29 or more)^[7] and socioeconomic status was assessed by Modified BG Prasad scale which is based on per capita monthly income (per capita monthly income*total monthly family income/total family members) and it can be used for both urban and rural population.^[8]

Statistical analysis:

Data was filled in Microsoft excel spreadsheet and was analyzed. Qualitative variables are presented as counts and percentages. Pearson's chi-square test, Student t-test, ANOVA analysis were used to compare the distribution of categorical variables among the two or more groups. P<0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Table 1. Psychosocial and demographic profile of suicide attempters

Psychosocial and demographic Parameters	Observations
Mean Age	30 Years
Male: Female Ratio	1.25:1
Marital Status	(%)
Married	Male 29(46.8) Female 33 (53.2)
Unmarried	Male 27 (71.1) Female 11 (28.9)
Employment Status	
Unemployed	67%
Employed	33%
History Of Psychiatric Illness	
Present	78%
Absent	32%
Prior history Of Suicide Attempt	
Present	13%
Absent	87%
Mode Of Suicide Attempt	
Poisoning	90%
Hanging	8%
Drowning	2%
Socioeconomic Class (Modified BG Prasad Scale 2023)	
I (₹ 8822 And Above/Month)	7%
II (₹ 4411 – 8821/Month)	32%
III (₹ 2647 – 4410/Month)	36%
IV (₹ 1323 – 2646/Month)	23%
V (₹ 1322 And below)	2%

Table 1 shows socio-demographic data among the suicide attempters. The mean age was 30 years (range 18 - 65 years). The mean age of the suicide attempters was 30 years with a range from 18 years to 65 years. The ratio of male and female patients was 1.25 :1. There was high prevalence of married females (53.2%) and unemployed individuals (67%) among suicide attempters. It was observed that significant number of patients had past history of psychiatric illness (78%) and also had history of suicide attempt 13%. The most common mode of suicide attempt was poisoning (90%) (due to easy availability) followed by hanging (8%) and drowning (2%). Most of them belonged to middle class (36%) as per modified BG Prasad scale for year 2023- social class-III).

Table 2. Results of Psychiatric assessment scales

Scales	Percentage
Suicide Intent Scale (SIS)	
low intent (score 15-19)	20
medium intent (score 20-28)	20
high intent (score 29+)	60
Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS SCORE)	
< 75	22
≥ 75	78
Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS 21)	
Depression Severity	
mild (score 10-13)	3
moderate (score 14-20)	40
severe (score 21-27)	57
Anxiety Levels	
moderate (score 10-14)	37
severe (score 15-19)	58
extremely severe (score 20+)	5
Stress Levels	
moderate (score 19-25)	38
severe (score 26-33)	61
extremely severe (score 34+)	1

In **Table 2**, psychiatric assessment of suicide attempters was done to assess the risk of future attempt using standard and validated psychiatric assessment scales. Maximum individuals had high suicide intent (60%) followed by medium (20%) and low intent (20%). As per DASS 21 scale, analysis of data depicts severe depression levels (57%) followed by moderate (40%) and mild levels (3%). Most people had severe anxiety levels (58%) followed by moderate levels (37%) and least were extremely severe (5%). Maximum individuals also reported severe stress (61%) followed by moderate levels (38%) and least in extremely severe (1%). On Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS), most of the individuals had score ≥ 75 (78%) indicating severe psychiatric symptoms and 22% of them had score ≤ 75. In our study, majority of suicide attempters were of high intent (60%), severe depression (57%), had severe anxiety levels (58%), severe stress levels and had high BPRS scores (78%).

Table 3. Association of Age group with psychological state determined by standard psychiatric assessment scales

History Of Psychiatric Illness	Age Group (In Years) In Percentage					p value
	≤ 20	21-30	31-40	41-50	>50	
present	16	34	16	2	6	0.029
absent	8	9	2	5	2	
SIS						0.001
low intent	3	5	4	3	5	
medium intent	3	8	5	2	2	

high intent	18	30	9	2	1	
DASS 21						
Depression Severity						0.02
mild	0	1	1	1	3	
moderate	10	17	7	3	3	
severe	14	25	10	3	2	
Anxiety Levels						0.030
moderate	6	16	9	2	1	
severe	16	25	8	5	3	
extremely severe	2	2	1	0	4	
Stress levels						0.021
moderate	9	17	6	6	3	
severe	15	26	12	1	4	
extremely severe	0	0	0	0	1	
BPRS SCORE						0.014
<75	9	7	1	4	1	
≥ 75	15	36	17	3	7	

As depicted in table 3, among suicide attempters, most common age group was 21-30 years of age. In age group 21-30 years, previous history of psychiatric illness was observed highest (34%) was statistically significant ($p=0.029$). High suicide intent was also observed in this age group (30%) which was statistically significant ($p=0.001$). In the age group of 21-30 years, severe depression (25%) with $p=0.02$, severe anxiety levels (25%) with $p=0.030$ and severe stress levels (26%) with $p=0.021$ was observed and was statistically significant. Also, high BPRS scores observed in this age group ($p=0.014$) were statically significant.

Table 4. Association of Marital status with psychological state determined by standard psychiatric assessment scales

Marital Status					
History of Psychiatric Illness	Married (Percentage)		Unmarried (Percentage)		p value
	male (percentage)	female (percentage)	male (percentage)	female (percentage)	
present	27(32.9%)	28(34.1%)	21(25.6%)	6(7.3 %)	0.036
absent	2(11.1%)	5(27.8%)	6(33.3 %)	5(27.8 %)	
SIS SCALE					0.0008
low intent	14		0		
medium intent	0		1		
high intent	48		37		
DASS 21					
Depression Severity					0.013
mild	0		5		
moderate	27		13		
severe	35		20		
Anxiety Levels					0.025
moderate	27		8		
severe	33		25		
extremely severe	2		5		
Stress levels					0.031

moderate	26	13	
severe	36	21	
extremely severe	0	4	
BPRS SCORE			0.042
< 75	9	12	
≥ 75	53	26	

Table 4, depicts about the association between marital status of the suicide attempters with the psychiatric tools used in the study. Among suicide attempters, the prevalence of previous history of psychiatric illness was high among married females (34.1%) and unmarried males (32.9%) which was statistically significant (p=0.036). High suicide intent was observed in married individuals (48%) which was statistically significant (p=0.0008). Severe depression (35%) with p=0.013, severe anxiety levels (33%) with p=0.013, severe stress levels (36%) with p=0.025 were observed in married individuals and was statistically significant. Also, high BPRS score (26%) was observed in married individuals (p=0.042) and was statistically significant.

Table 5. Association of Employment status with psychological state determined by standard psychiatric assessment scales

History Of Psychiatric Illness	EMPLOYMENT STATUS		p value
	Unemployed (Percentage)	Employed (Percentage)	
absent	16	2	0.029
present	51	31	
SIS SCALE			0.022
low intent	5	7	
medium intent	3	3	
high intent	59	23	
DASS 21			0.02
Depression severity			
mild	0	3	
moderate	22	18	
severe	45	12	
Anxiety levels			0.021
moderate	26	8	
severe	39	19	
extremely severe	2	6	
Stress levels			0.04
moderate	24	12	
severe	43	18	
extremely severe	0	3	
BPRS score			0.021
<75	17	2	
≥ 75	50	31	

Table 5, depicts about the association between employment status of the suicide attempters with the psychiatric tools used in the study. Among suicide attempters, the prevalence of previous history of psychiatric illness was high in unemployed individuals (51%) which was statistically significant (p=0.029). High suicide intent was observed in unemployed individuals (59%) which was statistically significant (p=0.022). Severe depression (45%) with p=0.02, severe anxiety levels (39%) with p=0.021, severe stress levels (43%) with p=0.04 were observed in unemployed individuals and was statistically significant. Also, high BPRS score (50%) was observed in unemployed individuals (p=0.021) and was statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

This observational cross-sectional study offers a comprehensive analysis of the socio-demographic, psychological, and clinical profiles of individuals who have attempted suicide, with a particular focus on age, gender, marital status, employment, psychiatric comorbidity, and the method of suicide attempt. We used standard and validated psychiatric assessment scales to evaluate it. The findings emphasize on the multifactorial nature of suicidal behavior.

In our study, most common age group among suicide attempters was 21-30 years (43%) with mean age of 30 years as similar study conducted by Samiksha Sahu et al where a similar trend was observed among young adults constituting the most vulnerable age group due to psychosocial stressors ,academic pressure and relationship issues.^[9] Male: female ratio was 1.25 :1 where males were slightly more (56%) than females (44%) echoing the findings of Chaudhary et al who reported higher suicide attempt rates among males.^[10] Suicide attempt was mainly observed in married individuals (62%), particularly women suggesting it to be a source of chronic stress and lack of mental health support for relational difficulties. Most of suicide attempters were unemployed (67%) indicating employment as a protective factor. History of prior suicide attempts were present in 13% of cases, indicating elevated future risk of committing suicide. Previous history of psychiatric illness was found in 78% of cases. On psychiatric assessment scales, high suicide intent was observed in 60% of cases on SIS scores similar to findings reported by Kanchan et al, where high SIS scores were significantly associated with past psychiatric history.^[11] High BPRS scores ≥ 75 was recorded in 78% of study population indicating severe psychiatric symptoms. Severe depression (57%), severe anxiety (58%) and severe stress levels (61%) was observed on DASS-21 scale. Most of the patients belonged to middle class (36%) as per modified BG prasad scale. Poisoning was the predominant mode of suicide attempt accounting for 90% of cases followed by hanging 8% and drowning 2% aligns with findings of study conducted by Robin victor et al from various regions where poisoning is a common method due to easy availability.^[12] Individuals in the 21-30year age group exhibited history of psychiatric illness (34%) and significantly greater suicidal intent and psychiatric symptom severity, as evidenced by SIS ($p=0.001$) and BPRS scores($p=0.014$). Individuals aged ≤ 30 years showed a significantly higher prevalence of severe depression, anxiety, and stress as measured by DASS-21 scale. Married individuals showed significantly higher psychiatric illness prevalence (67%) compared to unmarried individuals ($p=0.036$). High suicide intent was more

common in married group (48%) versus unmarried ones (37%), with a statistically significant difference ($p=0.08$). Severe depression, anxiety and stress were significantly more prevalent in married participants. Unemployment was significantly associated with high suicidal intent, observed in 72% of unemployed individuals. It was significantly correlated to severe depression ($p=0.02$), anxiety($p=0.021$) and stress($p=0.04$) and high BPRS score ≥ 75 in 74.6% of patients reflecting high level of psychiatric distress.

LIMITATIONS:

1. **Single-Center and Limited sample size:** The research was conducted at a single tertiary care hospital and involved a sample size of 100 patients While this allows for focused data collection, it limits the generalizability of the findings to broader populations across different geographic, cultural, and socioeconomic settings. Overwhelming poisoning cases were observed.
2. **Cross-Sectional design:** The study employed a cross-sectional design, which captures a snapshot in time but does not allow for establishing causality. Thus, while associations between variables were identified, causal relationships cannot be confirmed.
3. **Reliance on Self-Reported Data:** Several components, including psychological assessments using DASS-21 and SIS, relied on self-reporting. This introduces the potential for bias due to underreporting, overreporting, or recall inaccuracies, especially under emotional distress or stigma.
4. **Exclusion of Completed Suicides:** The study focused solely on survivors of suicide attempts. Consequently, the psychological and demographic profiles of individuals who completed suicide were not captured.
5. **Lack of Longitudinal Follow-Up:** No follow-up was conducted to track recurrence, treatment adherence, or psychosocial recovery. This limits the ability to assess long-term outcomes and the efficacy of post-attempt interventions.

CONCLUSION:

Our study reveals the complex interplay of demographic, psychosocial, and clinical factors behind suicide attempts. Suicides were more common among younger age group, males, married females, unemployed individuals and patients belonging to middle socioeconomic class. Suicide intent and psychological stresses (depression, anxiety, stress and severe psychiatric symptoms) were more common among

younger population, married individuals, unemployed ones. The findings call for a multidimensional suicide prevention strategy involving psychiatric support, socio-economic rehabilitation and increased public awareness and address risk factors in high-risk groups.

Conflict Of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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